
Book Reviews

Xavier, S. Basil. . Basil's Ethnophilosophising in India: A Study on Arunthathiyars (Series I). New Delhi: Authors Press, 2020. ISBN: 978-93-89824-88-9. pp. 376. Hardbound. ₹ 1400, \$ 70.

This book is the outcome of the author's strenuous research conducted on ethnophilosophy of Arunthathiyars, Ethnophilosophy consists of shared beliefs, values and traditional wisdom of an ethnic group. It is found in their wise-sayings, proverbs, stories, mythology, rituals and religion. Ethnophilosophy is considered as a property of a community rather than an activity of an individual.

One of the most marginalised sub-sections among Dalits in the State, Arunthathiyars have largely remained underdeveloped with poor literacy. They cluster caste groups ,previously called as chakkiliyars and some more caste names and are one of the oldest caste groups, known to be first inhabitants of southern India and Tamil Nadu, according to DNA research done by Indian Academy of Sciences.

The first part deals with the ethnographic data of Arunthathiyars who are mostly scavengers and cobblers, the 'dalits of the dalits' in Tamil Nadu. Their counterparts in the other parts of India may be Madhigas, Mangs, Bhangis, Chamars, Mochis and others.

The second part deals with ethnophilosophy which is culled out from their mythical, religious, ritual, historical, professional and identity consciousness. This is the study of their 'collective consciousness'. It is an enquiry on 'popular consciousness'. Hence

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it is a research on “folk” philosophy, philosophy of ‘little tradition’, ‘subaltern’ philosophy and philosophy of the ‘periphery’ or ‘margin’.

This book tries to excavate the ethnophilosophy of Arunthathiyars by delving deeper into their folk/popular consciousness (348). The ethnography of Arunthathiyars presented in the third chapter is based on works in Tamil and on author’s own research in five districts of Tamil Nadu. The fourth chapter deals with the ethnography of Arunthathiyars culled out critically from Western missionaries and colonial officials (p. 350).

The next chapters deal with the mythical, religious, ritual, historical, professional and identity consciousness of Arunthathiyars . In this book the false history of Arunthathiyars is deconstructed and the true history is constructed.

The author shows successfully that the cult and worships turn out to be the “weapons of the weak” (p. 350). The author notes that in the 19th and 20th centuries Arunthathiyars are identified as cobblers and scavengers. The author argues that in the past Arunthathiyars were leather artisans who enjoyed high social status (p. 352). Later when the British explored hide and skin to England the indigenous and college leather industries of Arunthathiyars became extinct and destroyed their profession.

The book also proves that scavenging was not their traditional job. When their profession collapsed and when they were made paupers by the policies of the colonial government, they were forced to take up scavenging, as discussed in the section “anthropology of scavenging.” The book succeeds in a new kind of “identity construction” for the Arunthathiyars . It also deals with the relationship between construction of identity and their popular consciousness.

From a philosophical point of view, the book laments that only classical (‘great tradition’) is considered philosophy and the ordinary people’s world-views and consciousness are not taken seriously by researchers.

The author proves conclusively that the Arunthathiyars did not come from Andhra Pradesh but were original inhabitants of Tamil Nadu and they fought against the colonial powers, a fact largely ignored by the historians of freedom struggle (p. 355).

The author also shows that Arunthathiyars are the “subaltern

scientists” since their technological knowledge and craftsmanship were “outstanding and excellent” (p. 356). The scientific role of salt in keeping the wet skin from rotting was discovered by them several centuries ago. Their role in constructing irrigation bucket was commendable.

The data and facts obtained are philosophically interpreted towards the end of the book. It also talks of “boundary situation” and how boundaries are crossed (p. 353). The crossing of social boundaries and the resultant cruelty of the ‘upper’ caste is also discussed in the book.

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On the whole we can say that the book is a significant step towards the study of subaltern philosophy, the need for developing a subaltern consciousness and identity, which alone can liberate people from their internal and external bondage. This book makes a significant contribution to the Arunthathiyar community! Thus this critical book is highly recommended for students and scholars of philosophy, sociology, anthropology, theology and ethnography.

Goretti Amaladoss, Maria. (2020). Awake: Empower the Dropout. Palayamkottai: St. Xavier College of Education. ISBN: 978-93-84192-14-3. pp. xxiv=390 ₹200/-

“The empowerment of women through education: a comparative study of high school educated women and women dropouts at Kancheepuram in Tamil Nadu, under the guidance of Dr. Myrtle Barse.

Education widens one’s understanding, imagination and creativity and makes a person confident of facing life and its issues, in the end, bringing about peace, progress and prosperity for all. (xix-xx)

This work consists of 10 sections. After the introduction, the second chapter situates the status of women in Tamil Nadu and particularly in Kancheepuram district. The next chapter deals with issues related to empowerment of women as a process. The fourth chapter deals with the impact of education on women empowerment. The author affirms that education “essentially involves opening

the mind, enhancing self-esteem and self confidence, building a sense of positive self-worth, accessing information and tools of knowledge and acquiring the ability to negotiate with this unequal and unjust world from a position of strength” (45). Rosenberg’s self-esteem scale is used in the study. The next chapter deals with the drawbacks of dropout women and education. The causes of dropout are elaborately discussed (p. 335).

The next chapter deals with the socio-economic and religious backgrounds of the women in the field of study. The seventh chapter explores the levels of self-esteem among the educated and drop-out women in a detailed manner. The eight chapter studies the knowledge levels of both dropout and educated women in terms of six parameters: health, hygiene, family planning, human rights and politico-economic system. The author points out that school education was mostly “delinked from “actual life, especially that of women” (p. 47).

The patriarchal structure of Indian society and culture is studied in the next chapter. The author shows that education of women facilitates the freedom of movement and is an important indicator of women empowerment. The author also shows that women have favorable attitude towards girl’s education. The final chapter focusses again on patriarchy that is accepted as way of life in Kancheepuram. For instance women-beating is accepted as a norm even by women themselves (345). The study points out that NGOs have played a crucial role in empowering and uplifting the women, in spite of the patriarchal mindset.

The study shows unambiguously that “education is an effective instrument of social and economic development and national integration” (p. 347).

This well-documented and researched work is a significant contribution to the situation of women in Kancheepuram and Tamil Nadu. This book is highly recommended for those involved in gender studies. Scholars of sociology, anthropology, social work, and ethnography will find the book highly rewarding.

Kuruvilla Pandikattu

Pandikattu, Kuruvilla. *Light for Life: Spiritual Insights for Contemporary World.* New Delhi: ISPCK, 2019. ISBN: 9789388945639; pp: 266 ₹ 295.

Can we be true to our own selves? Do we necessarily make compromises in living? How does God accompany us in our life journey? What is the role of spiritual depth in encountering our lives in its intensity? How does faith in God help us relate to fellow human beings better? These are some of the questions this book, meant to encourage us to live genuinely, deals with. In this way these are spiritual inputs for contemporary men and women.

As we know, life is a series of experiences contributing to our own self-understanding. This helps us to embrace the whole of reality gradually. The light that comes to us helps us to live our lives more deeply and fully. Thus the enlightened people were those who lived their ambiguous lives deeply and fully. They embraced the pain and found it deeply satisfying and painful. They rejoiced in everything, including in suffering and pain. Thus, to be alive is to be open to the tragic and ecstatic dimensions of our day to day life. Such an experience, even in its bitterness, will enlighten us. The light that emerges from life is symbolically seen as leading to our own fullness. These articles try to convey this sense of a committed and concerned spirituality that does justice to living together.

As such, these short essays are meant for a general audience, who may or may not be organisationally religious. They are meant to inspire a band of young men and women to think deeply about themselves, leading to deeper insights and wisdom.

Open-minded and visionary, these articles are meant to touch the daily life of busy people who are fully involved in the struggle and success of daily life. Mostly limited to 625 words, these articles attempt to provide them with both roots and wings: roots that will give them a sense of belonging to the rich Indian heritage and wings that will take them forward based on the spiritual depth.

Though the author gladly acknowledges his Christian commitment, he does not impose it on the audience. Trying to be objective and philosophical, as much as possible, the articles are an open invitation to search for deeper meaning and widen vision.

For clarity and convenience, these articles are roughly divided into nine Sections. The Spiritual Adventure; Socially Committed; Yearning for the Divine; Experiencing the Divine; Realising Human Values; Living Creatively; Light and Shadows; Psychological Depth of Being; Learning from Life

These articles presuppose that spiritual life has to be based on day to day experiences of ordinary people, and so God has to be found in our daily life. When we reflect on daily events, we can indeed be open to the most profound mystery that guides us forward. A cautious and courageous attitude is necessary for this search. Truly optimistic and open-ended, these articles urge the readers to find the depth of existence in the ordinary things of the world and thus make the sacred emerge from the mundane. In that sense, even though some of us refuse to believe in God, as a species, we can claim to be a sacred species capable of experiencing the depth of light and love: the only one who can and needs to make such a claim.

Thus the title “Light for Life” implies that we can always find traces of light even in the utmost darkness that we experience, which is the basic claim and understanding of the Christian faith. This gives us hope and joy in the shadows that accompany us. May the insights in this book offers rays of light in our lives, sometimes burdened and heavy! For we are always in search of the Divine. Or more correctly, the Divine is in search of us! At every moment! In all situations! So, the glimpse of light at every moment of life (and death)! That enables us hopeful and joyful. Highly recommended for thinking Christians to nourish their souls.

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